

Stage 2: Interview Question Guide

For Stage 2 of the semi-structured interview study reported in the paper "What You See is What You Trace - A Two-Stage Interview Study on Traceability Practices and Eye Tracking Potential"

Introduction and Background

1. Introduction of the interviewer: briefly explain content and structure of the interview, anonymous analysis of responses and right to cancel or request data deletion at any time
2. Do you agree with this interview being recorded?
3. Please describe your role and tasks concerning software projects.
4. How long (in years) have you been working in or with software projects?
5. How long have you been working in this project?

Part 1: Requirements Management

6. Which artifact types do you work with? (e.g., textual requirements, models, UML, user stories, project plan, code, tests, etc.)
7. Which tools do you use during a normal work day?
 - a. Which of these tools do you use how much if you only consider "productive" working time (excluding meetings)? If you had to put percentage numbers on them?
8. Is there a specific "workflow" when you are working with requirements?
9. Which document types or artifacts do you often use in parallel? I.e., one is accessed directly after the other or both are shown on the screen simultaneously.

Part 2: Traceability Practices, Benefits and Problems

10. How is traceability implemented in this project?
 - a. If not sure what the term means, give short explanation.
 - i. Software Traceability is defined as the ability to link together related artifacts from different sources within a project.
 - ii. Traceability of requirements is the ability to describe and follow the life of a requirement in both a forwards and backwards direction.
 - iii. Its advantages include requirements coverage analysis, change impact analysis or dependency analysis.
 - b. In what way? What is traced? Are there different types of links? Which granularity?
 - c. How much manual effort is required? Is it implemented for the entire project or only certain parts?
 - d. How well does it work? Are there any problems like poorly maintained or missing links?
11. Are you using any of these trace links? If yes, how? For what purpose?
12. What is your personal opinion regarding traceability? Do you think that the benefits outweigh the costs?

Part 3: Tracing with Eye Tracking

13. The next questions are asked in a more open way. For that I will explain a new approach for the automatic detection of trace links by using eye tracking. The idea is that eye tracking data are automatically recorded while people – may it be requirements engineers, architects, developers or testers – normally work on their tasks. By unintrusively recording gaze data in the background, it can be detected which artifacts are often looked at consecutively. Thereby, links are being generated between those artifacts. This way, when looking at that

artifact again you can directly access related ones by following these detected links. E.g., when you look at a JIRA ticket, then at a part of a specification page and then to another related document, this gaze path could be processed to trace links between those artifacts.

14. Do you have any questions about the approach? Did you understand the concept? Did anything remain unclear?
15. Generally speaking: what do you think of the approach? Do you see a use for it? Do you have any concerns?
16. Do you see a use case for this approach for the way you personally work?
 - e. Would it be possible to detect useful links based on gaze data recorded during your tasks?
 - f. Would any of these detected links be useful for your tasks?
17. Would you prefer that these links are shown to you as suggestions, i.e., when you often look between certain artifacts, a dialog comes up and asks if you want to create a link between these two? Or would you prefer for it to be done completely automatically even though there might be incorrect links included as well which you would need to correct later on?
18. Would you prefer to only have your own gaze data processed to links or also see the implicitly created links of others?
19. Do you think that it might make sense to collect links in a context-sensitive manner? I.e., that links depend on the person's role or the task that they were working on while the trace link was collected?
20. Could you see yourself having an eye tracker running while you are working or would you have concerns regarding privacy and observation?
 - g. Which preconditions would need to be fulfilled for you to feel comfortable with detecting trace links based on gaze data?

Conclusion

21. Is there anything you would like to add? Do you have any questions or remarks?
22. Would you be interested in receiving the results of the study by email?